

RECORD-KEEPING AS PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICE AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined how principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The equity theory of John Stacey Adams (1965) was used to guide the study. One research question and a corresponding null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 254 school principals and 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample was 739 teachers from the three Senatorial Districts, selected through the clustered sampling technique. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Administrative Practice of Record-keeping Questionnaire" (PAPRQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPO)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analysed using Simple Linear Regression analysis. The research hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance. The results showed that principals' administrative practice of record-keeping significantly predicts teachers' job performance in lesson preparation, lesson delivery, classroom management, use of instructional materials and students' assessment in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school principals should make serious efforts in the area of record-keeping and management. Records relating to students' admission, staff personnel, curriculum, school disciplinary measures, facilities procurement and maintenance, academic and social activities, internal and external examination results, school-community relations, and parent-teacher association activities among others should be properly and safely kept for reference purposes. Likewise, the Ministry of Education and State Secondary Education Board should as a matter of priority ensure that schools are provided with all the required records for the smooth and effective administration of the public secondary schools.

Keywords: Record Keeping, Job Performance, Public Secondary Schools, Management.

1 Introduction

Background to the Study

In the administration of secondary schools, the principal is central. The principal is the man at the helm of the affairs who receives all praises when success is attained and blames when the school fails. Considering the nature of man, if the principals of the Nigerian secondary schools fail to effectively carry out their administrative duties, most of the school facilities will be in a state of decay, and teachers may be ineffective thereby leading to poor performance of students in the public secondary schools. Administrative leadership is a complex process that entails working in a collegial, collaborative relationship with teachers and other educators to improve the quality of teaching and learning in schools while also promoting teachers' long-term development. (Beach and Judy, 2000).

The effective performance of any school system largely depends on the nature of its administrative setup as well as control. The realization of the goals and objectives of a school cannot be entirely suspended from its administrative skills and competence. To Mohammed, Edu and Etoh (2020) the principal, who is at the center of all operations in the secondary school system, has a long list of responsibilities, ranging from effective delegation of authority to staff training and student management, as well as school plant management. Students' management should incorporate the guidance services aimed at assisting them to study effectively as they are an essential component of the school that serve as indicators for rating the extent of achievement or failure of the school. The school principal plays the most essential role in a school, in almost all of its operational activities such as internal management vis-à-vis maintenance of high standards of educational practices, ensuring a balance with the surrounding external environmental conditions within which the school operates. The principal dictates the extent to which work is done in the school system (Abari and Mohammed 2018). The administrative leadership of the school principal is a critical factor in the success of a school's improvement initiatives and the overall effectiveness of the school.

The principal's primary role is to ensure that all students learn and succeed. (Lunenburg and Orstein 2008). It is against this background that the researcher decided to consider principals' administrative practice of record management in relation to teachers' job performance.

According to Seniwoliba, Mahama, and Abilla (2017), record management is the efficient and methodical handling of records (both paper and electronic) throughout their life-cycle, from creation to disposal. The systematic control and effective use of records throughout their life cycle is thus the basis of records management. Records management is defined by Danso (2015) as the systematic control of an

organization's records throughout its life cycle in order to meet operational needs, statutory and fiscal requirements, and community expectations. Such systematic control is exercised over the creation, storage, maintenance and disposal of school records. The researchers defined record management as the systematic process of generating, storing, managing and retrieval of information. There are many importance of effective record management.

Ekpoh and Eze (2015), opine that teachers' job performance involves all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve the desired effects on students. It involves the extent to which the teacher participates in the overall running of the school in order to achieve the expected objectives and goals of the school. In other words, performance is the accomplishment of school goals.

Darling - Hammond (2010) defined an effective teacher as one who is intellectually challenging, motivating students, setting high standards and encourages self-initiating learning. Anderson (2007) viewed effective teachers as those teachers who achieved the goals set for them or goals set for them by others like the Ministry of Education. Effective teachers are very important for students learning. However, teachers' effectiveness is difficult to define since there has not been a consensus agreement on what measured quality teacher (Stronge, Ward and Grant, 2011). However, it is possible to measure some teachers' attribute like interaction with student, teaching strategy, motivation, content knowledge and classroom management through qualitative research approach. These teachers' attributes could act in a long way to determine teachers' effectiveness

Statement of the Problem

Researchers have attempted to investigate problems pertaining to the teaching and learning process, taking into account the opinion of stakeholders at all levels that the country's education is in crisis. Despite the fact that numerous studies have been undertaken and recommendations made in order to address the problem of lowering educational standards, particularly in public secondary schools, the problem persists. As a result, the government, principals, instructors, and students are all accused of contributing to the fall in educational quality.

Teachers' professional laxity has been noted in public secondary schools, which is embarrassing. Some teachers consider teaching as the final resort for the hopeless, and they are simply sticking on to hunt for better opportunities outside of school. In other words, they are in the teaching profession because they cannot find another work that they enjoy. As a result, persistent cases of lateness to school and classes, irregular and unauthorized movement from duty posts, failure to mark and correct students' work, non-use of instructional materials, inability to convincingly explain

difficult concepts to students, and, most importantly, poor classroom management skill pose a significant obstacle to the achievement of educational goals in public secondary schools.

"Could the negative attitude of teachers toward their job performance be a result of the principals' administrative practice of record-keeping in public secondary schools?" One would wonder. This is an important question since teachers are the main drivers of the educational system, and their effective job performance determines the system's success or failure. In light of this, the researcher opted to look into how principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria's Akwa Ibom State. In other words, how well does the administrative practice of record-keeping by principals predict teacher performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Purpose of the Study

The study was designed to examine the extent to which principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Question

To what extent does principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The extent to which principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

Scope of Study

The scope of this study covered all the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria during the 2020/2021 academic year which ended in July 2021. The investigation centered on the principals' administrative practice of record-keeping. Job performance of teachers was measured in terms of lesson preparation, lesson delivery, use of instructional materials, classroom management, and students' evaluation in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework.

Equity Theory

Equity theory was outlined by workplace and behavioral psychologist John Stacey Adams in 1965. He posited that jobs involve a continuous assessment of how much

‘give and take’ there is between employer and employee. The basic premise of this model is that job satisfaction and motivation result from a fair balance between an employee’s ‘inputs’ and ‘outputs.’ The common examples of inputs according to Adams are i. hard work ii. Skill level iii. Enthusiasm for the job iv. Supporting colleagues and, v. Personal sacrifice. Common outputs include: i. financial compensation ii. Recognition and reputation iii. Praise iv. Job security v. Other intangible benefits.

The greater the imbalance (or ‘inequity’) between the two, the less likely a strong, productive relationship will emerge between employer and employee. Besides, dissatisfaction can get worse if the ratio between inputs and outputs is deemed to be more imbalanced when compared to others.

The relevance of this theory to the study is its emphasis on the expectations of the employees (teachers) for effective job performance (inputs) and employers (principals) as administrative practices (outputs). The implication of this theory is that teachers are expected to be at their best in terms of commitment to their duties and the principals need to recognize and reward hard work as a way of encouraging teachers to improve or sustain effectiveness.

2.2 Principals’ Administrative Practice of Record Keeping and Teachers’ Job Performance

Ayodele (2002) sees school records as “pieces of information on relevant events about a school”. Education law demands that every educational institution should keep certain school records. These records are administrative records and teachers’ professional records. There are other records not required by law, but which are kept because they provide a useful source of information not only for members of the school community but also for other stakeholders. Employers may be interested in having particular information about students’ academic achievements, parents may be interested in how their children behave and perform in the school. Some ex-students may write requesting information about their career while in school, auditors may be interested in checking on details of financial transactions, and inspectors may need to go through the record of work of a particular teacher who is facing disciplinary action. The principal too may need to collate some information about a student or member of staff to back up a case to be presented to the school Board for or against a teacher.

There are two types of records that a secondary school can keep. These are statutory and non-statutory. Statutory school records are those records that are mandatory or compulsory under the law to be kept by each school as such they are expected to be

kept by all schools Alabi (2017). Under the education law in Nigeria, the following are some of the statutory records to be kept in schools; Admission Register, Daily Attendance Register, Diary of Works, Log Book, Lesson Note or Plan, Time-Table, School Budget Record, Visitor's Book, Corporal Punishment Book, Continuous Assessment Book, Time Book, Testimonial and Transfer Certificate Book, National Policy on Education, Examination Records, etc. Non-statutory records, on the other hand, are not mandatory to be kept but they are nevertheless equally important and useful for record purposes for the schools that can keep them. Such records if kept in schools usually help the principal and his management in the day-to-day administration of the school's affairs. Among such records are: Inventory Book, Stock Book, Requisition Book, Duty Roster Book, Movement Book, School Calendar, Staff Minutes Book, Staff Record, Physical Development Record, Health Record Book, Accounts Record, The Cash Book, Fees Register, Payment Voucher, Announcement Book, PTA Minutes Book, Record of Progress, Staff Union Minutes, Cooperative Society Record, etc. The list of the records is in exhaustive. The more the need for having an accurate keeping of necessary information on any area of administration of a secondary school, the more the necessity to create a record for such imperative areas.

Considering the statutory records kept in schools, there are some that are of great importance teachers' job performance which is the problem under consideration. Some of such records are as follow:

- i. **The Log Book:** This is a daily record of significant happenings and events in the life of a school. Events that are recorded in the log book include resumption and vacation for the term, sports and founder's day's activities, school excursions, changes of staff, examinations, names of important visitors and purpose(s) of visiting, PTA meetings, school routine inspection, etc. This book gives a summary of the historical development of the school. The record is absolutely kept and handled by the principal and it is out of bounds to other teachers. The book is at times referred to as "black book" and it is always kept under lock and key.
- ii. **Syllabus/Curriculum:** Each school must have the approved syllabus/curriculum which contains topics to be treated for each subject, for each class and for each year of the course. At the secondary school level, the syllabus or curriculum is prepared by the Ministry of Education and the examining bodies such as West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). The syllabus/curriculum is usually kept in the office of the school principal or vice principal (academics).

- iii. **Teachers' Record of Work (Diary):** This is a record of work showing what area of the syllabus/curriculum in a subject a teacher has covered. The record is kept by each teacher and must be produced on demand. It is important that each teacher enters in the record all the topics taught in the subject weekly and submit to the principal through his head of department for checking, signature and date. This important record is very useful when a teacher is transferred and another teacher has to take over his job. The teacher taking over would not have problem in identifying at what point he should start his job.
- iv. **Lesson Plan/Notes:** Every subject teacher is expected to prepare his plan or notes of teaching on each subject for the class(es) he has daily. The notes are expected to be comprehensive enough to be understood by any other teacher in the same subject area to be able to use it to teach in case the teacher is officially engaged or indisposed that he cannot teach the subject. The lesson plan or notes are expected to be examined "marked" and approved by the head of department before it can be used by the teacher. The lesson plan is a mark of level of preparation by a teacher for his teaching hence it is expected that such a teacher should be able to deliver his teaching well.
- v. **The School Time-Table:** This record shows the daily activities/routine of the school. The time-table shows the time the school opens daily, the time for morning devotion, recesses (short and long breaks) and closing time. It also shows the time a subject or a class is to hold; the teacher, the class and the classroom. The school time-table is usually displayed in the office of the principal or vice principal (academics), head of department's office, the staff room, on the notice board(s) and each teacher should be conversant with it or is expected to extract the time-table as it affects his teaching functions and other duties in the school.
- vi. **Staff Record Book:** This record contains the list of all the staff members in a school with their biographical data. It contains such information as when a teacher joins the staff of the school, his age, qualifications, experience, date of assumption of duty, date of resignation / transfer and the reason for such.
- vii. **Teachers' Time Book:** This is filled by each teacher on daily basis. It shows how punctual and regular a teacher is in school. It is always kept in the school office where every teacher will see it, write his/her name, time he/she arrives school and append his/her signature. Also, at the close of the school or before the close of the school for the day, the teacher still has to indicate the time he/she is leaving the school. The principal or any of his designated vice has to check the time book at the end of the day and enter remarks.

- viii. **Staff Movement Book:** This is a book in which any teacher going out of the school during the school hours enters his name, destination, the reason for going out and the time he is going. The time he returns is also indicated when he comes back. This serves as a control measure to reduce unauthorized movement of teachers during official hours of work.
- ix. **Staff Minutes Book:** This records the minutes of staff meetings. Staff are expected to meet from time to time to take decisions on how they can be more productive and effective in the discharge of their duties. This record helps the teacher to know the future line of action and to follow same in line with the decision they had jointly taken together in the staff meeting.
- x. **National Policy on Education:** This is a must for every secondary school. It contains all necessary information about every level of education in Nigeria. Every secondary school teacher needs to know what the government's policy is on secondary school education so that they can fit in properly and contribute meaningfully to the system.

Ajayi and Ayodele (2002), Oyewobi and Alabi (2002) identified the following as very important for keeping and maintenance of school records.

- i. The records must be full and complete. They must contain total and whole information not bits or parts as bits or part information will lead to wrong decision and eventual falsehood.
- ii. They must be truthful and honest. School records must not contain lies. Those who fill the records must tell the truth. Decision and actions taken on lies will yield wrong results.
- iii. They must be available when needed. School records are not personal property of any teacher or even the principal to be kept at his home or be taken away from school just anyhow. They are properties of the school and must be kept in school always hence proper security must be provided for them.
- iv. They must be used to take appropriate actions. Each record has a purpose. As such appropriate records must be used to make appropriate decisions and actions. For example, in identifying the most punctual student, the attendance register is the most appropriate record to consult. For some decisions and actions, more than one record may be consulted.
- v. They must be original. School records must contain what is going on in the school not just copying what was going on in another school. This is why the school records are unique to each school because they present what are all and

facts as far as each school is concerned. School records are not imagined or fictionalized; they are records of realities on the ground in the school.

- vi. They must be kept safe from excessive humidity and heat that can spoil them. They must be kept in good condition for many generations to see and read. Adequate security must be provided for school records so that they can be easily retrieved in good and perfect conditions at any time.

Salami, Alabi, and Okemakinde (2002), Okpetu and Peretomode (2005) and Paseda (2009) have all identified the importance of keeping school records. According to the authors, the significance of school records keeping are:

- i. It is an important aspect of (school) administration. It is compulsory and can never be jettisoned
- ii. It provides useful information on the progress and development made within the school.
- iii. For providing information for parents and guardians who may seek information regarding the general conduct and academic performance of their children and wards at school.
- iv. To enable the teacher to know something about his students and through this be in a better position to assist them academically, morally, socially, etc. in addition to being able to predict their behavior and provide needed information to whoever may need it.
- v. For research purposes in education and in other fields.
- vi. For planning and budgeting purposes
- vii. To enable the school authority provide necessary data about the school which may be required from time to time from the proprietor / proprietress or other agencies of education.
- viii. To enable the school authority provide requested information to employer of labor who may need the services of the students for job placement.
- ix. To provide useful information about any student intending to further his/her education in a tertiary institution.
- x. For assessment of teachers and principals.
- xi. To save the school from any unnecessary embarrassment as well as a legal tussle.
- xii. For the purpose of continuity in school administration.
- xiii. For effective and efficient management of the school.

There are certain problems with record-keeping in schools. Ajayi and Ayodele (2002) have identified such as i. Lack of uniformity of record keeping. ii. Apathy/laziness on the part of teachers to supply information or record information. iii. Lack of formal training/induction of teachers in record keeping. iv. Lack of continuity of records. v. Security problems i.e. destruction of records. vi. Fictitious/false information. vii. Inadequate record-keeping materials.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of the 254 public secondary school principals and all the 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in the three Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 739 teachers from the three senatorial districts (the thirty three Local Government Area) which formed 10% of teachers of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected through the clustered sampling technique where the state was grouped into the three Senatorial Districts. 10% of the total number of teachers in each of the three Senatorial Districts was further selected as sample through simple random sampling. Three students were also randomly selected to provide information on each teacher's job performance from each of the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom.

3.3 Instrumentation

Two instruments named Principals' Administrative Practice of Record-Keeping Questionnaire (PAPRO) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data from respondents (Teachers and students)

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Simple Linear Regression analysis for research questions and null hypotheses. The hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance.

4 EMPIRICAL RESULT

4.1 Answering the Research Question

Research Question: To what extent does principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Simple Linear Regression analysis was employed, and the data obtained is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis for the extent to which principals' practice of record keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Variable	R	R Square	Extent of Prediction	Remark
Principals' Record Keeping (x) Extent	.676	.457	45.7%	Moderate
Teachers' Job Performance(y)				

The entry in Table 1 reveals the R for the strength of the relationship and R^2 for the determination of the extent to which principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance. The R- Value of .676 indicates the extent to which the prediction occurs. The calculated R^2 of .457 which is the coefficient of determinant indicates that only 45.7% variability in effectiveness is predicted or contributed by principals' administrative practice of record keeping. This implies that principals' administrative practice of record keeping to a moderate extent, predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.2 Testing the Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis: The extent to which principals' administrative practice of record-keeping predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis for the prediction between principals' administrative practice of record keeping and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Source of Variation	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F-cal	Sig
Regression	70361.765	1	70361.765		
Residual	619.754	.000 ^b			
Total	83445.858	735	113.532		
	153807.623	736			

The entries in Table 2 revealed that the calculated F-value of 619.75 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 736 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which claims that the extent to which principals' administrative practice of record keeping predicts teachers' job performance is not significant is rejected. The result reveals that principals' administrative practice of record keeping significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of finding

The result shows that there is significant prediction between principals' administrative practice of record keeping and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This result means that principals' efforts to keep statutory records and making same available when needed by teachers for reference purposes contributes to a moderate extent to teachers' job performance especially in lesson planning, students' assessment and classroom management.

The relationship between record management and teachers' job performance is supported by Salami, Alabi, and Okemakinde (2002), Okpetu and Peretomode (2005) and Paseda (2009) who identified the importance of keeping school records as:

- i. It is an important aspect of (school) administration. It is compulsory and can never be jettisoned
- ii. It provides useful information on the progress and development made within the school.
- iii. For providing information for parents and guardians who may seek information regarding the general conduct and academic performance of their children and wards at school.
- iv. To enable the teacher know something about his students and through this be in a better position to assist them academically, morally, socially, etc. in addition to being able to predict their behavior and provide needed information to whoever may need it.
- v. For research purposes in education and in other fields.
- vi. For planning and budgeting purposes
- vii. To enable the school authority provide necessary data about the school which may be required from time to time from the proprietor / proprietress or other agencies of education.
- viii. To enable the school authority provide requested information to employer of labor who may need the services of the students for job placement.
- ix. To provide useful information about any student intending to further his/her education in a tertiary institution.
- x. For assessment of teachers and principals.
- xi. To save the school from any unnecessary embarrassment as well as legal tussle.
- xii. For the purpose of continuity in school administration.
- xiii. For effective and efficient management of the school.

Jonathan and Nwankwo (2020) revealed that the record storage practices adopted by principals for effective school administration included: dispersion of several copies of file in several locations, keeping of files, ensuring confidentiality of stored

document, keeping document in cupboards based on their subject matters, saving information in a computer system, using magnetic tape in storing information, labeling of files and keeping files in a cabinet drawer and steel shelves.

Odeniyi and Adeyanju (2020) opined that record management is an area of administrative practice that is concerned with achieving economy and efficiency in the creation, maintenance, use and disposal of records of an organization throughout its life cycle. Implementing good record management practices in schools would provide information for educational planners and administrators, serves as historical source for documenting history of the school. The researchers recommend that stakeholders should ensure timely update of record materials and finally, delegation and follow-up on record procedures should be given adequate attention by school principals. Alabi (2017) postulated that without keeping appropriate, adequate and relevant school records, there cannot be effective and efficient administration of secondary schools. This opinion is further stressed by Ibara (2010) who maintained that quality performance, task accomplishment, and measurable outcomes are increasingly important responsibilities, all of which depend on the accessibility of usable records. Without access to records, it is virtually impossible to determine responsibility for actions and to hold individuals accountable for their actions.

The finding of this study is in agreement with the opinion of Eghareuba and Omorigiwa (2006) who postulated that, principals who cannot enforce teachers to be at work on time are not effective, and that consistent absence of teachers in school will affect the realization of educational goals. Furthermore, the researchers asserted that, if principals do not keep teachers' records, then it will be impossible to know teachers who come late in order to enforce discipline of such teachers to be at work on time.

Similarly, the finding agrees with the view of Sunmola (2008) who states that keeping of time book exposes teachers' lateness to school or class. Teachers records can if kept adequately, be used for their performance appraisal to know their strength or weakness, whereby the principals can make recommendation for remedial services. This assertion is in line with the Study of Sule, Odu, Nkama and Adeyemi (2012) whose study revealed that keeping teachers' records can lead to improvement in their performance. This means that if principals keep teachers' records properly, it will improve their performance and can impact more on the principals' administration of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

5 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended among other things that school principals should make serious efforts in the area of record-keeping and

management. Records relating to students' admission, staff personnel, curriculum, school disciplinary measures, facilities procurement and maintenance, academic and social activities, internal and external examination results, school-community relation, parent – teacher association activities among others should be properly and safely kept for reference purposes. Likewise, the Ministry of Education and State Secondary Education Board should as a matter of priority ensure that schools are provided with all the required records for the smooth and effective administration of the public secondary schools.

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